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The Financing of Associations in the Italian Regions during the Period 2005-2022

It decreased on average by 29.97%

Istat calculates the value of association financing. The variable is calculated as the number of people aged 14 and over who have financed associations in the last 12 months out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2005 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of association financing in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place by value of association financing in 2022 with an amount of 23.4 units, followed by Lombardy with an amount of 17.1 units and from Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 16.3 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont with an amount of 14.1 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 13.3 units and Liguria with a value of 13.1 units. Calabria closes the ranking with a value of 6.8 units, followed by Puglia with a value of 5.9 units and Sicily with a value of 5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the financing of associations between 2005 and 2022. Campania is in first place for the value of the percentage change in the financing of associations between 2005 and 2022 with a corresponding value of -3.33%. to a variation from an amount of 9.1 units up to 8.8 units. Lazio follows with a variation equal to an amount of -8.9 units corresponding to a variation from an amount of 14.6 units up to a value of 13.3 units. In third place is Basilicata with a percentage variation of -13.14% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 13.7 units up to a value of 11.9 units. In the middle of the table are the Marche with a percentage variation equal to -25.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 19.6 units up to a value of 14.7 units. Sicily follows with a value of -25.37% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.7 units up to 5 units. In eleventh place are Lombardy with a variation of -31.6% corresponding to a reduction from 25 to 17.1 units between 2005 and 2022. Calabria closes the ranking with a percentage variation of -40, 87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 11.5 units up to 6.8 units or equal to -4.7 units. Puglia follows with a percentage variation equal to -42.72% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 10.3 units up to a value of 5.9 units between 2005 and 2022. Emilia Romagna follows with a variation percentage equal to -42.75% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 26.2 in 2005 up to 15 units in 2022. On average between 2005 and 2022 the percentage variation in the financing of associations in the Italian regions decreased from 18 .42 units up to 12.90 units corresponding to -29.97%.

Percentage change in the financing of associations in the Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. The financing of associations decreased in all Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2022. In particular, the financing of associations decreased in the North with a value of -32.49%, in the North-West with -28.05%, North-East with a value of -38.08%, Central Italy with -25.25%, Southern

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Italy with -25.96%, South with -23.36%, Islands with -31.63%. However, despite the overall reduction in the financing of associations in the Italian macro-regions, there are still significant differences between southern and northern regions. In fact, the value of the financing of associations in Southern Italy is 42.3% lower than in Central Italy, 49.1% lower than in the North-East, 48.4% lower than in the North-West, 48.8% lower than North.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we apply the k-Means clustering algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of three clusters:

- Cluster 1: Puglia, Calabria, Campania, Molise, Sicily, Abruzzo, Lazio, Basilicata;
- Cluster 2: Lombardy, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Piedmont, Sardinia, Marche, Umbria, Liguria;
- Cluster 3: Trentino Alto Adige.

If we consider the value of the average of the clusters it is possible to identify the following ordering of the clusters, namely: Cluster 3>Cluster 2>Cluster 1. We note that cluster 3 is made up of a single region, namely Trentino Alto Adige. This is followed by Cluster 2 made up of the regions of the Center and North with the sole exception of Sardinia. In last place is Cluster 1 made up of southern regions with the exception of Lazio. Therefore there is a significant distinction between the regions of the Center and North which have medium-high levels of financing of associations compared to the regions of Southern Italy which have medium-low levels of financing of associations.

Conclusions. The value of association financing has decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions. However, despite the general decrease in financing of associations, there is a distinction between regions of Central and Northern Italy with high values of the observed variables and regions of Southern Italy with reduced values. The reduction in the value of association financing shows a change in the character of Italians. In fact, Italians have generally always been considered a generous and supportive people. The reduction in the financing of associations shows an erosion of social capital which has occurred especially in the regions of Central and Northern Italy.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Regione	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	17,8	16,8	18,9	19,5	17,7	18,4	19,6	17,2	12,9	17,9	19,1	15,8	17	15,9	14,8	16,1	13	14,1
Valle d'Aosta/Valle d'Aoste	22,9	19	17,6	22,7	18,9	22,2	22,9	21,1	16,1	16,7	22,9	19,7	16,6	18,6	20,3	17	12,5	15,5
Liguria	16,3	16,7	17,2	17,2	17,5	18,2	16,8	17,1	13,1	15,1	16,6	16,9	18,4	15	16,4	15,3	14,2	13,1
Lombardia	25	23,4	21,1	20,1	22	23,3	23,3	20,6	17,3	19,7	19,6	20,1	17,5	18,5	16,3	19,3	15,9	17,1
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	38,3	32,9	32,2	33,8	31,9	33,3	34,5	31,3	27,6	29	32,5	30,2	29,6	29,2	26,8	28,3	21,9	23,4
Veneto	24,6	21,2	21,6	20,3	20,6	22,1	22,1	20,4	17,8	17,7	17,1	19,3	17,2	18,5	15,4	17,8	15	15,4
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	21,6	20,8	21,2	22,2	20,3	24,7	24,1	20,3	17	18,3	21,4	19,8	19,8	18,7	20,7	19,5	15,3	16,3
Emilia-Romagna	26,2	25,1	24,5	24,8	23,1	24	23,3	19,1	18,8	19,3	19,2	17,7	20,2	20,3	18,3	18,9	16,4	15
Toscana	24,9	23	25,4	18,8	24,1	26,5	21	19	20,7	20,8	19,3	19,2	17,9	20,8	18	18,2	16	15,7
Umbria	19,2	20	16,2	19,9	17	17,9	19,1	15,1	12,9	16	17,1	17,2	18,4	16,1	14	14,5	13,8	12,5
Marche	19,6	16,1	18,5	15,8	19,2	17,8	20,5	15,4	13,6	17,1	19,8	18,4	16,8	16	15	15,2	13	14,7
Lazio	14,6	13,7	12	13,3	13,9	15,5	13,6	11,1	9,6	12	11,1	11,8	11,4	12,5	11,2	11,8	10,3	13,3
Abruzzo	15,6	11,2	12,6	10,1	10,5	14,2	13,8	9,7	9,7	12,5	12,8	12,4	10,8	10,9	11,3	10,7	11,1	12,6
Molise	11,9	10,5	11	8,7	9,3	13,7	9,2	10,7	8,6	11,6	7,9	10,6	11,5	8,9	9,1	12,7	7,3	9,3
Campania	9,1	8,3	8,6	6,6	8,1	7,5	6,8	6	5	5,7	6,1	7,3	7,9	7,4	7,4	7,6	5,6	8,8
Puglia	10,3	11,1	9,8	9,9	9,5	9,8	8,3	8,7	7,7	6,7	9,7	10,8	7,8	8,4	8,4	9,4	7,8	5,9

Basilicata	13,7	15,9	15,2	13,2	14,5	14,7	13,4	11,4	10,6	11,6	11,7	11,8	13,3	13,9	12,3	12,9	7,5	11,9
Calabria	11,5	9,6	9,1	9,5	10,1	12,3	9,1	8,2	6	7,8	7,7	8	6,6	8	7,5	6,3	6,3	6,8
Sicilia	6,7	7,8	6,5	5,7	6,8	6,5	7,8	5,8	4,6	5,9	6,6	5,3	6,2	5,5	6,1	6,1	4,7	5
Sardegna	18,6	18,4	19,1	18,4	21,9	20,2	17,7	17,3	14,4	17,5	17,9	16	16,6	15,9	13,9	14,1	11,3	11,6

	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	23,7	22,1	21,6	21,2	21,2	22,5	22,5	19,9	17	19	19,4	19,1	18,6	18,6	17	18,6	15,5	16
Nord - ovest	22,1	21	20,3	19,7	20,3	21,4	21,6	19,3	15,7	18,7	19,2	18,6	17,7	17,4	16,2	18	14,9	15,9
Nord - est	26	23,6	23,6	23,4	22,5	24,1	23,9	20,8	19	19,4	19,7	19,7	19,8	20,2	18,1	19,3	16,2	16,1
Centro	19	17,5	17,5	15,9	18,1	19,5	17,3	14,5	13,9	15,7	15,2	15,4	14,7	15,8	14	14,4	12,9	14,2
Mezzogiorno	10,4	10,1	9,7	8,7	9,8	9,9	9,1	8,1	6,8	7,8	8,6	8,8	8,5	8,3	8,2	8,4	6,8	7,7
Sud	10,7	10	9,7	8,7	9,3	9,9	8,5	7,8	6,7	7,3	8,3	9,1	8,3	8,4	8,3	8,6	7	8,2
Isole	9,8	10,5	9,7	8,9	10,7	10	10,3	8,7	7,1	8,8	9,4	8	8,8	8,2	8	8,1	6,4	6,7